

Effect of Mother Tongue-Based Self Learning Module on the Academic Performance

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Abstract. This study sought to determine the level of academic performance of the learners. Eventually, it also aimed to determine the magnitude of the effect of mother tongue-based self-learning on learners' academic performance. The study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade three learners – 34 from section A comprised the controlled group, and 26 from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B had identical grades. The study used non-random assignment of subjects where all learners from sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. The study utilized the new regular learning modality. It was blended learning where the teacher gave modules while meeting the learners face-to-face but adhering to the Inter-agency Task Force (IATF) protocols. The researcher met the learners with parents' permission during face-to-face sessions to follow up on what had been covered in the modules. The study revealed that using mother tongue-based self-learning modules had increased the academic performance of grade three students. It also revealed a magnitude of difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Mother Tongue-Based Self Learning.
2. Academic Performance.
3. Blended Learning.

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1. Introduction

Mother tongue-based self-learning recognizes the significance of utilizing a child's native language as the primary medium of instruction, particularly in the early stages of education. This approach aligns with research that underscores the cognitive and academic benefits of learning in one's mother tongue (UNESCO, 2016). By leveraging the language children are most familiar with, educators can facilitate a deeper understanding of concepts and foster a stronger foundation for learning (Aguilar, 2021). The core of this approach is using one's native language as the primary medium for learning. This ensures that learners can fully understand and engage with the material without the added challenge of learning a second or foreign language. In mother tongue-based self-learning, individuals take responsibility for their learning process. They identify their learning goals, select resources, and determine the pace and direction of their studies. Learners have autonomy over their learning journey, deciding what to learn, how to learn it, and when to review or practice. This fosters independence and self-

reliance in the learning process (Aguirre, 2024). Mother tongue-based self-learning allows individuals to tailor their learning experiences to their preferred styles and methods. Learning in one's mother tongue often entails culturally relevant and relatable content. This can enhance understanding and retention of information by connecting new knowledge to existing cultural frameworks and experiences. While self-directed, mother tongue-based self-learning doesn't necessarily mean learning in isolation. They adjust their approach based on their experiences and feedback, ensuring continuous improvement and growth. Mother tongue-based self-learning emphasizes the importance of using one's native language as a powerful tool for acquiring knowledge and skills autonomously, effectively, and in a culturally relevant context (Akinaso, 2023). Academic performance in one's mother tongue can vary significantly depending on factors such as the quality of education, teaching methods, resources available, and the individual's proficiency in the language. Research has shown that students generally perform better academically when taught in their mother tongue, especially in the early years of education. This is because language is closely tied to cognitive development, and students are better able to comprehend and retain information when it is presented in a language, they are most familiar with (Akinsolu, 2020). Furthermore, proficiency in one's mother tongue can also have long-term benefits, including higher literacy rates, improved critical thinking skills, and overall academic achievement. However, it's essential to recognize that academic performance is influenced by factors beyond language alone, such as socioeconomic status, parental involvement, teacher quality, and access to educational resources. Therefore, while mother-tongue instruction can positively impact academic performance, it is not the sole determinant (Akiri Ugborugbo, 2019). As a result, the implementation of MTB-MLE in the Philip-

pinas is considered an example for the rest of the region. The adoption of MTB-MLE became the beginning of a more significant movement for the DepEd and Congress that solely relies on the findings of various and previous studies that elucidate the benefits of the mother tongue as a language of instruction (Burton, 2013). These studies deduced that minority language pupils who gained literacy in their first language or mother tongue experienced higher academic achievement than students who learned in a second or third language. They suggested that second and third languages can be acquired more quickly if a foundation in the first language is established early (Balogun et al., 2019). In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, the same problem is encountered in the learners' poor mother tongue language proficiency; the researcher, being a teacher in the early grades, explores to determine the effect of mother tongue on the academic performance of the learners. Hence, this study.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. Mother Tongue Based Education—

Mother-tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE) has been recognized as an effective approach to improving academic performance, especially in multilingual regions. Research indicates that learning in one's mother tongue enhances cognitive development, improves comprehension and retention, and fosters a strong foundation for learning additional languages (Ball, 2020; Benson, 2020). This method connects students with their cultural heritage, motivating them and reducing dropout rates, ultimately leading to better academic outcomes (Benson, 2019; Cummins, 2020).

MTB-MLE programs involve the local community in curriculum development, fostering a supportive learning environment. Effective communication between teachers and students in a common language enhances understanding and classroom interaction (Cummins, 2020). How-

ever, the success of these programs depends on teacher training, curriculum development, and community involvement (Skutnabb-Kangas, 2020).

1.1.2. Self-learning in Mother Tongue—Self-learning in the mother tongue has several advantages, including better understanding and retention of content, increased motivation, and faster skill acquisition (UNESCO, 2018). It enhances students' self-efficacy and parental involvement in education, leading to better academic outcomes (Baker, 2011; UNESCO, 2018). However, self-learners might face challenges such as lack of structured learning environments, social interaction, native-like pronunciation, and cultural nuances (Krashen; Hymes; Brislin; UNESCO, 2023).

1.1.3. Challenges in MTB-MLE Implementation—Several challenges hinder the implementation of MTB-MLE, including difficulties in translation, inadequacy of instructional materials, and mandatory compliance with educational policies (Valerio, 2015; Alexander, 2019). Teachers often struggle with the transition to using mother tongue as a medium of instruction due to insufficient localized instructional materials and varying perceptions of its impact on English skills (Aguilar, 2021; Aguirre, 2024).

1.1.4. Impact on Academic Performance—Mother-tongue instruction in early education is increasingly supported worldwide, improving learning outcomes and fostering inclusion (Banjoko et al., 2018; Farooq et al., 2021). In the Philippines, MTB-MLE has shown benefits such as better comprehension, engagement, and real-world application of concepts (Koles et al., 2018). However, challenges include a lack of teaching materials and linguistic diversity among students (Koles et al., 2018; Gaultney, 2017).

Therefore, Mother-tongue-based multilingual education has significant potential to improve academic performance by providing a culturally relevant and supportive learning environ-

ment. Its success depends on effective teacher training, curriculum development, and community involvement. Despite challenges, the benefits of MTB-MLE in fostering better comprehension, engagement, and academic success are well-supported by research.

1.2. Synthesis—The above-stated review of significant literature discussed the prevalence of the problem under study in different contexts. It also discussed methodologies for solving the current issue. Findings and recommendations were presented to resolve the problem. This literature backed up the occurrence of the problem, and different localities presented solutions. They also served as a roadmap to guide the researcher in conducting the study.

1.3. Theoretical Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on the Sociocultural Theory of Vygotsky (1978), who argued that cognitive abilities are socially guided and constructed. He believed that cognitive development is influenced by cultural and social factors. He emphasized the role of social interaction in the development of mental abilities, e.g., speech and reasoning in children. As such, culture serves as a mediator for forming and developing specific abilities, such as learning, memory, attention, and problem-solving. Vygotsky's theory comprises concepts such as culture-specific tools, private speech, and the zone of proximal development. Vygotsky strongly believed that community plays a central role in the process of "making meaning." Cognitive development is a socially mediated process in which children acquire cultural values, beliefs, and problem-solving strategies through collaborative dialogues with more knowledgeable members of society. This is supported by the theory of Academic Performance proposed by Elger (2007) who described 'perform' as an ability to produce a valued result and 'performer' as an individual or a group that engages in collaboration while the level of performance as the location in an academic journey. Accord-

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study

ing to Elger (2007), there are six components of performance levels, and they are: level of knowledge, levels of skills, level of identity, personal factors, and fixed factors and proposed three axioms for effective performance as a performer’s mindset, immersion in an enriching environment, and engagement in reflective prac-

tice. The theory of performance challenges educators to improve their performance through empowerment to help others learn effectively and grow. This type of learning will foster quick success and produce knowledge that will influence society.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study sought to determine the level of Academic Performance of the learners. Eventually, it also sought to determine the magnitude of the ef-

fect of Mother Tongued Based Self Learning on the Academic Performance of Learners’ action initiated by the researcher on the academic performance of the research subjects. Moreover, it sought to answer to the following sub-problems:

- (1) What is the pre-test scores of the learners both from controlled and experimental groups?
- (2) What is the post test scores of the learners both from controlled and experimental groups?
- (3) Is there a significant difference in the post-test scores of the learners from controlled and experimental groups?
- (4) What is the magnitude of effect of the Mother Tongued Based Self Learning on the Academic Performance of learners?

1.5. Null Hypothesis—The null hypothesis in this study was tested at 0.05 level of significance. H01. The Online teaching of science approach had no effect on the academic performance of the grade three learners.

1.6. Significance of the Study—The results and findings of this study will be beneficial to the following: The Department of Education should know the results and findings of this study so that it can create a policy that considers online teaching an integral modality to

assist modular instruction in schools. Besides, the department will conduct a reorientation for all school leaders on the mechanics of online classes as a supplement to modular instruction given to learners. School Heads. As the school's manager, the school head needs to know the results and findings of this study to initiate a school-based program that would strengthen the implementation of online teaching to supplement the modular instruction given to learners. Teachers. The teachers should have gone the extra mile by conducting online classes to follow up on the lessons given to learners in the modules. Learners can be guided further if teachers give further instruction on the activities, they will do that are found in the module. Future Researchers. The results and findings of this study

will give insights to future researchers as to the importance of online teaching as an advantage for learners. Mother tongue education refers to any form of schooling that uses the language or languages that children are most familiar with to help them learn. Children learn first in a familiar language and then gradually add a second language. When it is time to incorporate a second language, children who learn through MTB programs build on existing language skills to understand what they are reading, improving literacy rates. Academic Performance refers to the grades of grade three learners who benefit from MTB-MLE online teaching. According to Wikipedia (2021), academic performance is the extent to which a student has attained his educational goals and is measured by assessment.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the manuscript's overall quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design, which was a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. A non-equivalent design

was good when the researcher had access to one group for experimentation (Vockel, 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are an intact group of learners. This design was represented as follows:

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade three learners – 34 were from section A, which comprised the controlled group, and 26 were from section B, which is the experimental group. The composi-

tion of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study used the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. Since it was pandemic time, the experiment was conducted based on the mechanics of Mother Tongue-Based Self Learning.

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- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	No. of Pupils	
1	Section A	34
2	Section B	26
Total		60

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new regular learning modality. It is a blended learning where the teacher gives a module and at the same time, meets the learners face to face while adhering to the protocols of the Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher met the learners with parents’ permission during face-to-face sessions for a follow-up of what had been printed in the module. The pre- and post-performance tests consisted of a 50-item self-learning module that eventually

determined the academic performance of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful in assessing the effect of mother-tongue-based self-learning on the academic performance of learners. On the other hand, a post-test was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the effect of mother tongue-based self-learning on learners’ academic performance, the following continuum, based on the DepEd rating system, was used.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of the data-gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking permission to conduct this research study, which was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Davao Del Sur and to the school principal concerned. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the DepEd Schools Division Superintendent and to the principle of Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, Dr. Nelson C. Lopez, CESO V, the researcher constructed

a questionnaire and had it validated by the experts, preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher administered a pretest to both the controlled and experimental classes and eventually commences her experiment in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered a

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation, after which the researcher made an analysis and interpretation of the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—In this study, we used several statistical tools to analyze and interpret the data. We used the mean to describe the academic performance of the subjects in both the

controlled and experimental groups during the pretest and posttest. We employed a t-test for uncorrelated samples to determine the significance of the difference between the mean scores of the pretest and post-test in the experimental and controlled groups. Additionally, we utilized Eta square to measure the effect of mother tongue-based self-learning on the learners' academic performance.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the problems in this study. They are thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners, and the Significant Relationship of the Pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade three

learners. The controlled group got a mean of 58.08 or Beginning, while the experimental group got a mean of 61.24 or Beginning.

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	34	14.58	58.32	Beginning
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	26	15.36	61.44	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during the pre-test, the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the control group, although both belonged to the Beginning level. This finding is congruent with the idea of Farooq et al. (2021), who cited that education in the mother tongue is a key factor for inclusion and quality learning, and it also improves learning outcomes and academic performance. This is crucial, especially in primary school, to avoid knowledge gaps and increase the speed of learning and comprehension. Moreover, most importantly, multilingual education based on the mother tongue empowers all learners to participate fully in society. It fosters mutual understanding and respect for one another and

helps preserve the wealth of cultural and traditional heritage in every language worldwide. Mother-tongue-based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) has been increasingly recognized as a practical approach to improving academic performance among learners, particularly in regions where multiple languages are spoken. Research suggests that learning in one’s mother tongue enhances cognitive development, providing a solid foundation for learning additional languages and subjects. When students learn a language they understand well, they are more likely to engage actively with the content, leading to better comprehension and retention (Ball, 2020).

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Post-test	34	20.51	82.04	Developing
Experimental Group				
Post-test	26	21.61	86.44	Approaching Proficiency

Table 2 shows the post-test scores of the grade three learners. The controlled group got a mean of 20.51, or Developing, while the experimental group gained a mean of 21.61, or Approaching Proficiency. The table shows that during the post-test, the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.25 from 15.36 to 21.61. This means that the experimental

group performed far better than the controlled group. This finding is congruent with Koles et al. (2018), who cited that the students were more engaged in learning, had better comprehension, and could apply concepts to real-world situations. This success story is a testament to how effective mother tongue-based instruction can be. Academic performance depends not only on a student’s ability to learn the material but also

on their ability to understand spoken and written language, their ability to convey their verbal and written knowledge, and their literacy skills such as reading, writing, and spelling. Kids start developing the precursor skills needed to read, write, and spell as young as two years old. Students' performance will suffer if those skills are later developed or not developed. MTB-MLE allows students to connect with their cultural heritage and identity, fostering a sense of pride

and belonging. When educational materials are culturally relevant and meaningful, students are more motivated to learn, which can lead to improved academic performance. Learning to read and write in one's mother tongue before transitioning to other languages has improved literacy skills. When students are literate in their mother tongue, they can more easily transfer those skills to additional languages, leading to better overall academic performance (Benson, 2020).

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	22	-5.47	.0356	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.47 with a p-value of .0356, which is less than the .05 level of significance. This means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post-test scores of the grade three learners. This implies that the use of a mother tongue-based self-learning module contributed to the academic performance revealed by the scores of the grade three learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Callier et al. (2001), Lubuagan (2010), and Pinnock (2010), who conducted studies that showed the benefits of MTI to children who are educated using the Mother Tongue or native dialect. Both Callier et al. (2001) and Lubuagan (2010) observed that using the language spoken at home and inside the classroom during the early years of schooling produces better and faster learners. Pinnock (2010) also noted that the foundations for learning begin with what is familiar. He con-

cluded that the child's first language should be used as a primary language of instruction across the curriculum. The local culture and environment should be at the center of the learning process and that using mother tongue ensures an efficient learning process (Gaultney, 2017). When teachers and students share a common language, communication becomes more effective, leading to better understanding and interaction in the classroom. This facilitates a supportive learning environment where students feel comfortable asking questions and seeking clarification, ultimately improving their academic performance. MTB-MLE programs often involve the local community in curriculum development and implementation, which fosters a sense of ownership and support for education initiatives. When communities actively engage in the educational process, students are more likely to receive the necessary support and resources to succeed academically (Cummins, 2020).

Table 4 highlights the test of the late afternoon program on the letter recognition skills of Grade Three learners. It generated an Eta2

value of 0.446, which signifies a significant effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy to enhance the academic performance

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade three learners

N	t-value	Eta ²	Descriptive Value	Decision
60	-4.43	0.446	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

of Grade three learners. Fostering academic excellence in grade three learners is essential for their cognitive, social, and emotional growth, and it lays the groundwork for future success. Self-learning in one’s mother tongue offers several advantages contributing to more effective and engaging learning experiences. While there might not be many direct studies focusing explicitly on ”mother tongue self-learning,” the advantages of self-learning and the importance of the mother tongue in education have been extensively researched. Learning in one’s mother tongue facilitates better understanding and retention of content. Research by UNESCO suggests that students grasp concepts more readily when taught in a language they understand well

(UNESCO, 2018). Self-learning in the mother tongue can boost motivation and engagement with educational materials. According to a study published in the *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, students are more motivated to learn when educational content is presented in their mother tongue, leading to increased academic success. Learning in one’s mother tongue can expedite the acquisition of new skills. A Cummins (2000) study found that students who develop strong literacy skills in their first language are better equipped to transfer those skills to additional languages, resulting in faster overall language acquisition (Skutnabb-Kangas, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter summarizes the findings, conclusions, and recommendations drawn by the researcher after analyzing and interpreting the findings. This study sought to determine the effect of the mother tongue-based learning module on the academic performance of grade three learners. This study used a quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. A non-equivalent design is good when the researcher can access one group for experimentation (Vockel, 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the study subjects were intact learners. This study was conducted in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were 60 grade three students: 26 were from section A, which comprised the control group, and 34 were from section B, which is the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous; therefore, pupils of sections A and B have identical ranges of performance. This study used the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that using a mother tongue-based self-learning module has increased the academic performance of grade three students. It also revealed that there is a magnitude of difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade three students in both the controlled and experimental

groups are at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group are at the Developing level, while the post-test scores of the experimental group are at the Approaching

Proficiency level.

4.2. *Recommendations*—In light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching Grade Three students use a mother tongue-based self-learning module as a strategy to further develop learners' academic performance. Academic performance is a crucial indicator of a student's ability to understand and apply knowledge, shaping their educational journey, future career prospects, personal growth, and societal contributions. The school heads should promote the use of mother tongue-based self-learning modules, which would further enhance the academic performance of grade three learn-

ers, as revealed in the study. These modules are essential for fostering intellectual curiosity, equipping students with necessary skills, and preparing them to navigate the complexities of the modern world. A school policy about using mother-tongue-based self-learning modules can be issued. Moreover, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demonstrate teaching during LAC sessions using a mother-tongue-based self-learning module as a teaching strategy. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of mother tongue-based self-learning modules as a teaching strategy be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

- Aguilar, J. (2021). The language situation in the philippines: Facts and prospects [Retrieved December 4, 2010]. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 46(6), 412–470. http://www.perj.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=42:vintage-paper-mle-1948-1966&catid=10
- Aguirre, A. (2024). Parent and teacher opinions of bilingual education: Comparisons and contrasts. *The National Association for Bilingual Education Journal*, 9(1), 41–51.
- Akinnaso, F. N. (2023). Policy and experiment in mother tongue literacy in nigeria. *International Review of Education*, 39(4), 255–285.
- Akinsolu, A. O. (2020). Teachers and students' academic performance in nigerian secondary schools.
- Akiri, A. A., & Ugborugbo, N. M. (2019). Teachers' effectiveness and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in delta state, nigeria. *Studies on Home and Community Science*, 3(2), 107–113.
- Alexander, N. (2019). Language planning from below. In R. Herbert (Ed.), *Language and society in africa: The theory and practice of sociolinguistics* (pp. 56–68). Witswatersrand University Press.
- Ambatchew, M. D. (2020). Traversing the linguistic quicksand in ethiopia. In K. Menken & O. García (Eds.), *Negotiating language policies in schools: Educators as policymakers* (pp. 211–231). Routledge.
- Auerbach, E. R. (2020). Creating participatory learning communities: Paradoxes and possibilities. In J. Hall & W. Eggington (Eds.), *The sociopolitics of english language teaching* (pp. 143–164). Multilingual Matters.
- Backman, S. (2019). *Policy as practice: Local appropriation of language and education policies in lesotho primary schools* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Michigan State University.

- Ball, J. (2020). Enhancing learning of children from diverse language backgrounds: Mother-tongue-based bilingual or multilingual education in early childhood and early primary school years.
- Balogun, O. S., Oyelere, S. S., & Atsa'am, D. D. (2019). Data analytics on performance of computing students. *Proceedings of the 19th Koli Calling International Conference on Computing Education Research*, 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3364510.3366152>
- Bangko Sentral Pilipinas. (2018). Overseas employment statistics [Retrieved January 2, 2011, from <http://www.bsp.gov.ph/statistics/keystat/ofw.htm>].
- Banjoko, A. W., Yahya, W. B., Abiodun, H. S., Adeleke, M. O., Afolayan, R. B., Garba, M. K., Olorede, K. O., & Dauda, K. A. (2018). On the strength of agreement between students' initial and final academic performances in nigeria university system. *Nigerian Journal of Mathematics and Applications*, 24, 135–157.
- Bax, S. (2022). The social and cultural dimensions of teacher training. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 28(2), 165–178.
- Benson, C. (2019). Mother-tongue-based multilingual education: The key to unlocking global goals. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 16(4), 371–387. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790718.2018.1481541>
- Benson, C. (2020). The primary bilingual education experiment in mozambique, 1993 to 1997. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 3(3), 149–166.
- Brown, S. D., Tramayne, S., Hoxha, D., Telander, K., Fan, X., & Lent, R. W. (2018). Social cognitive predictors of college students' academic performance and persistence: A meta-analytic path analysis. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 72(3), 298–308.
- Cummins, J. (2020). *Language, power, and pedagogy: Bilingual children in the crossfire*.
- Farooq, M. S., Chaudhry, A. H., Shafiq, M., & Berhanu, G. (2021). Factors affecting students' quality of academic performance: A case of secondary school level. *Journal of quality and technology management*, 7(2), 1–14.
- Fernandes, E., Holanda, M., Victorino, M., Borges, V., Carvalho, R., & Van Erven, G. (2019). Educational data mining: Predictive analysis of academic performance of public-school students in the capital of brazil. *Journal of Business Research*, 94, 335–343.
- Gaultney, J. F. (2017). The prevalence of sleep disorders in college students: Impact on academic performance. *Journal of American College Health*, 59(2), 91–97.
- Giunchiglia, F., Zeni, M., Gobbi, E., Bignotti, E., & Bison, I. (2018). Mobile social media usage and academic performances as a counseling guide for the university prospective admission seekers. *Proceedings of the 35th International Business Information Management Association Conference (IBIMA)*, 11935–11945.
- Ibidoja, O. J., Ajare, E. O., & Jolayemi, E. T. (2017). Reliability measures of academic performance. *International Journal Of Science for Global Sustainability*, 2(4), 59–64.
- Iyanda, A. R., Ninan, O. D., Ajayi, A. O., & Anyabolu, O. G. (2018). Predicting student academic performance in computer science courses: A comparison of neural network models. *International Journal of Modern Education & Computer Science*, 10(6).
- Jolayemi, E. T. (2019). On the measure of agreement between two raters. *Biometrical journal*, 32(1), 87–93.

- Junco, R. (2022). Too much face and not enough books: The relationship between multiple indices of facebook use and academic performance. *Computers in human behavior*, 28(1), 187–198.
- Koles, P. G., Stolfi, A., Borges, N. J., Nelson, S., & Parmelee, D. X. (2018). The impact of team-based learning on medical students' academic performance. *Academic Medicine*, 85(11), 1739–1745.
- Skutnabb-Kangas, T. (2020). *Linguistic genocide in education – or worldwide diversity and human rights?*
- UNESCO. (2018). *Mother tongue matters: Local language as a key to effective learning*.
- UNESCO. (2023). If you don't understand, how can you learn? unesco education for all global monitoring report policy paper 24.